

ISic4411

Epitaph for Kratisstos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Contributors

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Autopsy

Metcalfe 2016 visited museum

Last Change

2020-05-26 - Jonathan Prag created the file from template and publications

Place of origin (ancient)

Abacaenum

Place of origin (modern)

near Tripi

Provenance

Tomb 18/42 of the necropolis in contrada Cardusa

Coordinates

38.065190, 15.114380

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Tripi, Museo Archeologico Santi Furnari di Tripi, inventory ME23435

Physical Description

Three joining fragments of a stele of the local sandstone, forming part of a eptymbion ('type B')

Dimensions

Height 82 cm

Width 31 cm

Depth 15.5 cm

Layout

Single line of Greek letters filling the width of the stone

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain wide letters: kappa has arms of almost full length, not quite joining the vertical; rho is closed; alpha broad with straight bar; sigma has horizontal top and bottom bars, joined by a curving stroke rather than two distinct diagonals; omega sits very slightly above the line, is circular and open with short arms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: NA mm

Text

1. Κρατίσσω

Apparatus

text of Sofia 2018

Translation (en)

(Tomb) of Kratisstos

Commentary

The standard form of the name Κράτιστος [<http://clas-igpn2.classics.ox.ac.uk/>

[cgi-bin/lgnp_search.cgi?name=%CE%9A%CF%81%CE%AC%CF%84%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%82](http://classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgnp_search.cgi?name=%CE%9A%CF%81%CE%AC%CF%84%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%82)] and the feminine form Κρατιστώ [http://classics.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/lgnp_search.cgi?name=%CE%9A%CF%81%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B9%CF%83%CF%84%CF%8E] are attested principally in Athens, Taras and Olynthos, but also elsewhere - not however in Sicily. The open form of omega is potentially compatible with a late C4 date, but the form of the sigma is not readily paralleled so early.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

- Bacci, G.M., Coppolino, P. 2009. La Necropoli di Abakainon: primi dati. Messina. At 27 fig.14
- Sofia, G. 2015. Abakainon. Nella dimora di Ade. La necropoli in contrada Cardusa a Tripi. Terme Vigliatore (ME). At 113 fig.115
- Sofia, G. 2018. Nuove iscrizioni funerarie dalla necropoli di Abakainon. *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 206: 103-112. At 107 no.1 and fig.2

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